

Composition of Prussian and Turnbull's Blues. Part III.

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It has been shown in a previous communication (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240) that Prussian and Turnbull's blues tend to assume a similar composition on account of the mutual oxidation and reduction involved in the reaction between ferric and ferrocyanide ions in the preparation of the former, and between ferrous and ferricyanide ions in the preparation of the latter compound. Support to this view has been adduced by quantitative estimations of iron and cyanogen contents in Prussian and Turnbull's blues prepared under various concentrations of iron and ferrocyanogen salts, and by studying the change of their composition with time. It has also been qualitatively shown (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 325) by examining the filtrates that mutual oxidation and reduction do take place under certain conditions between the reactants.

In this paper an attempt has been made to elucidate further the nature of the compositions of Prussian and Turnbull's blues through the absorption spectrographic study of the solutions of these substances in a suitable solvent and correlate the spectrographic observations with those already published in the previous communications.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Standard solutions of ferric chloride, ferrous sulphate, potassium ferro- and ferricyanides were prepared. Respective solutions of known molecular concentrations were mixed with each other in equivalent proportions and the precipitates filtered for preparing fresh Prussian and Turnbull's blue in 24 hours. In the case of the aged preparations, the reacting solutions after being mixed together were allowed to age for about five weeks in stoppered bottles. The precipitates of Prussian and Turnbull's blues thus prepared either fresh or aged, were washed free from soluble impurities with cold or slightly tepid distilled water and dried in a current of hot air. The dried precipitates were then estimated for Fe_2O_3 by direct decomposition with heat in a porcelain crucible and the solution of the Prussian or Turnbull's blue was made in oxalic acid; the strength of the solution thus prepared was equivalent to 0.005 g. of Fe_2O_3 in 100 c.c. of oxalic acid containing 1.5 g. of $\text{H}_2^2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Absorption photographs were at first taken in the visible region with a constant deviation spectrograph (Adam Hilger's) by passing parallel rays from a point-o-lite source through the solution of Prussian or Turnbull's blue filled in a Baly's tube ; copper arc was taken on the plate as a reference spectrum to determine the wave-length where absorption had begun. From these photographs it appeared that the absorption shown by these substances was of a general, rather than selective character ; but on taking absorption photographs in the extreme red region it appeared that the absorption was selective and not general as was shown by the reappearance of the absorption band in the extreme red region, and for this reason it became necessary to study the absorptive properties of these substances in the visible, infra-red and ultraviolet regions.

The second set of photographs were taken with a grating spectrograph on panchromatic and infra-red sensitive plates. When infra-red sensitive plates were used the grating camera was exposed to the second order spectrum, the effective rays of the first order being cut off by placing a yellow filter on the slit. A tungsten filament lamp was used as a source in this case and the rays rendered parallel by a lens were allowed to pass through various thicknesses of the solution in the Baly's tube and photographs taken. Copper arc was taken as standard for reference; and for each absorption spectrum of the solution, that of the solvent was taken side by side for the same thickness, in order to discover the region where absorption due to the soluble substance actually began. Time of exposure for the solution was ten times that for the solvent, for reasons which have been discussed later. The point of equal intensities on the spectra of solvent and solution was observed under a comparator and its distance from a standard line on the photographic plate was measured. Then the wave-lengths where absorption took place were calculated from the dispersion curve of the instrument. Absorption photographs were taken in the same manner in the ultraviolet region by means of a quartz spectrograph (Zeiss) using excited hydrogen tube as a continuous source of light. The thicknesses of solutions have been taken in most cases in the order 1.0, 1.3, 1.65, 2.15, 2.8, 3.6, 4.6, 6.0, 7.7, and 10 cms. successively in a 10 cm. Baly's tube, because with such thicknesses the values of $\log K$ increased uniformly by about 0.1 unit with increasing thicknesses of the solutions, and therefore, the points are more conveniently plotted.

It is known quantitatively that in the case of solutions the fractions dI/I of the intensity of light absorbed by the solution is proportional to its thickness or the number of dissolved molecules, i.e. $-dI/I = K' \cdot c \cdot dD$, where D is the finite thickness of the layer and c the concentration of the solution. Hence, for a particular concentration c and thickness D of the solution, if we observe a point on the plate where the intensity of light through the solution has been weakened to one tenth, then we get the well known relation, $K = I/cD$, where c is given in mol /litre and D in cm. and K is the absorption coefficient of the substance.

On evaluating K as above from c and D and finding out λ from the dispersion curve as aforesaid, values of $\log K$ were plotted against the corresponding values of λ and the absorption curve for each solution thus obtained. The time of exposure for the solvent was, therefore, allowed one tenth of that of the solution, so that the point where equal intensities would appear on the spectra of the solvent and solution, it became evident that the intensity of light through the solution had been weakened to one-tenth and hence the formula $K = cD$ could be applied to evaluate the results under correct conditions.

In the following tables the values of K appear only for such thicknesses of the solution as have given points of equal intensities with the solvent. The other values of K for thicknesses which did not give points of equal intensity have been rejected. In the tables c , denotes concentration of the blue in terms of Fe_2O_3 per litre, D , the thickness of solution layer. Panchromatic and infra-red sensitised plates were used in obtaining the values in the visible and extreme red regions.

TABLE I.
Absorption in visible and red regions.

Name and composition.	c .	D .	K .	λ in visible region Violet end.	only Red end.
Aged Prussian blue $M/5 : M/5$.	0.05 g.	5 cm.	640.0	3693Å	5275Å
		6	533.3	3847	5198
		7	457.1	3924	5082
		10	320.0	4156	4812
		5	640.0	3809	5236
		6	533.3	3924	5198
Aged Turnbull's blue $M/5 : M/5$.	0.05 g.	7	457.1	4001	5082
		8	400.0	4079	5005
		9	355.5	4156	4967
		10	320.0	4195	4812

TABLE II.

Absorption in visible and extreme red regions.

Name and composition.	c.	D.	K.	Visible region.	Extreme red region.
Fresh Prussian blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	7.7cm.	4156	6935Å	7113Å
		10	3200	6742Å	?
Fresh Turnbull's blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	2.8	11428.5	?	6842Å
		3.6	8888.8	?	7112
		6.0	5333.3	6357Å	?
		7.7	4156	6202	?
		10	3200	5970	?
Aged Prussian blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	7.7	4156	6473Å	6957Å
		10	3200	6279Å	7228
Aged Turnbull's blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	7.7	4156	?	6687
		10	3200	6395Å	6995

TABLE III.

Absorption in ultraviolet region.

Name and composition.	c.	D.	K.	λ.
Aged Prussian blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	1.3 cm.	24615.4	2876Å
		2.8	11428.5	3130
		3.6	8888.8	3177
		4.6	6956.6	3379
		6.0	5333.3	3426
		7.7	4156	3459
		Aged Turnbull's blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	1.0
2.15	14885			2632
2.8	11428.5			2815
3.6	8888.8			2866
4.6	6956.6			3059
6.0	5333.3			3121
7.7	4156			3220

TABLE IV.

Absorption in ultraviolet region.

Name and composition.	c.	D.	K.	λ .
Aged Prussian blue <i>M/20 : M/20.</i>	0.005 g.	1.3 cm.	2615.4	2759Å
		1.65	19394	2801
		2.8	11428.5	2992
		3.6	8888.8	3059
		4.6	6956.6	3177
		6.0	5333.3	3219
Aged Turnbull's blue <i>M/20 : M/20.</i>	0.005 g.	2.15	14885	2730
		2.8	11428.5	2824
		3.6	8888.8	2946
		4.6	6956	3060
		6.0	5333.3	3111
		10	3200	3248

TABLE V.

Absorption in ultraviolet region.

Fresh Prussian blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	0.21 cm.	148850	2316Å
		0.36	88888	2373
		0.46	69566	2524
		0.60	53333	2660
		1.00	32000	2881
		2.15	14885	3050
Fresh Turnbull's blue <i>M/5 : M/5.</i>	0.005 g.	0.77	41560	2434
		1.00	32000	2528
		1.3	24615.4	2641
		1.65	19394	2716
		2.15	14885	2759

FIG. 1.

Absorption in visible region only for aged P. and T. blues (cf. Table I).

FIG. 2.

Absorption in visible and infra-red regions for fresh P. and T. blues (cf. Table II).

FIG. 3.

Absorption in visible and infra-red regions for aged P. and T. blues (cf. Table II).

FIG. 4.

Absorption in ultraviolet for aged P. and T. blues (cf. Table III).

FIG. 5.

Absorption in ultraviolet for aged
P. and T. blues (cf. Table IV).

FIG. 6.

Absorption in ultraviolet for
fresh P. and T. blues (cf.
Table V).

DISCUSSION.

From the accompanying absorption curves the following observations seem to be striking and may be deemed to throw some light on the composition and constitution of Prussian and Turnbull's blues:—

(a) The curves show that the absorptive power of Turnbull's blue is much greater than the Prussian blue when prepared fresh, and their absorptive power tends to be equal with the ageing of the preparations.

(b) That the shape of the absorption curves is quite similar, but for a little shift in the range of absorption.

(c) The absorption maxima appear in most of the solutions for the same values of K or in other words for the same thicknesses of the solution.

From the foregoing observations it becomes evident that the compositions of Prussian and Turnbull's blues tend to approach each other more closely when they are prepared by the ageing process than when fresh; and this is in close agreement with the results of chemical analysis already published (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240).

The shift of the absorption bands may be due to (i) the different proportion of Prussian and Turnbull's blues formed in course of the reaction between the reactants, iron and ferrocyanogen salts, and (ii) also due to the difference in the size of the particles of Prussian and Turnbull's blues when they are freshly precipitated. When the blues are prepared by ageing processes, both Prussian and Turnbull's blues seem to approach an average uniformity of size and composition in consequence of which their absorption curves approach each other closely.

As the shape of the absorption curve determines the constitution of a substance, it may be further suggested that the structural formulæ of these substances are similar to, if not identical with each other. The greater absorptive power of freshly prepared Turnbull's blue may be due to an excess of the ferrous molecules in which the ferrous iron is not saturated with regard to its maximum valency and therefore shows a greater absorption like many well-investigated organic compounds which, because of their unsaturated nature, show greater absorption than the saturated ones.

SUMMARY.

1. Absorption spectra of a few preparations of Prussian and Turnbull's blues have been studied in the visible, infra-red, and ultra-violet regions and their compositions elucidated from their absorption curves.

2. The absorption curves of Prussian and Turnbull's blue prepared fresh are much farther apart from each other than those of the aged compounds, from which it has been inferred that on ageing, these compounds approach each other in their compositions and these observations are in conformity with the results of chemical analysis already published.

3. From the similarity in the shape of the absorption curves of Prussian and Turnbull's blues it has been suggested that their molecular structures are similar and the greater absorptive power of

Turnbull's blue when freshly prepared has been suggested to be due to an excess of ferrous molecules where the ferrous iron is not saturated with regard to its maximum valency.

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Photochemical Reaction between Iodine and Oxalate.

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Amongst the photochemical reactions taking place in solutions, the iodine-oxalate reaction is one which has been investigated by several chemists. Since 1916, when one of the authors (Dhar, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amstardam*, 1916, **16**, 1097; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707; 1923, **123**, 1856; *Anal. Chim.*, 1919, **9**, 130) showed that this reaction is highly sensitive to light and that the dark reaction is slow and has a very high temperature coefficient, a great deal of work has been carried on this chemical change. Unfortunately, there is disagreement in the results obtained by different workers (Berthoud and Bellenot, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307;